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D3.1 Programme and material of the training for GEPI Committees

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACIISI	Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información
CE	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L.
EC	European Commission
FRCT	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI Committees	Gender Equality Plans Implementation Committees
GA	Grant Agreement
JSI	Jozef Stefan Institute
UB	University of Bucharest
UJK	Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce
ULPGC	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
UVSK SAV	Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej
WP	Work package

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable, entitled 'Programme and material of the training for GEPI Committees' presents the programme and material of the Training programme developed under the ATHENA framework delivered to the project Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees.

The document also introduces this figure of the GEPI Committee members, key elements for the facilitation and promotion of the institutional change towards gender equality at the ATHENA institutions, presenting their objectives, role, main tasks and composition.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable describes:

- The ATHENA GEPI Committee members, detailing their objective, role, main tasks, composition (**section 2**) and presenting the list of the established members for each ATHENA institution (**Annex I – List of the ATHENA GEPI Committee members**).
- Narrative and detailed information of the Training Programme delivered to the project GEPI Committee members (objective, structure, schedule, etc.) (**section 3**).
- Key material illustrative of the training programme, evaluation forms and templates to gather information on the specific trainings carried out by each ATHENA institution (**Annex II – Material of the training programme, Annex III – Evaluation form of the trainings 1 and 2 carried out via the ATHENA e-platform and Annex IV – Templates for the specific tailored trainings**).

2. ATHENA GEPI Committee members

One of the tasks within ATHENA is the establishment of the 'Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees', foreseen under the project Work Package (WP) 3 and to be set up at each project RPO/RFO implementing a Gender Equality Plan (GEP).

2.1 GEPI Committees: Objective and role

The **GEPI Committees are key actors for ATHENA** project and especially for each project partner organisation as they are involved together with the core consortium partners to **transmit co-produced knowledge on gender equality and facilitate and promote the institutional change** through the development and implementation of the GEPs. The implementation of the GEPs is a continuous process with a view to enhance and institutionalize gender equality in each ATHENA partnering organisation. To achieve gender equality in the ATHENA RPOs and RFOs, institutional transformations are needed and will lead to change the official holding composition, reducing women and men inequalities.

The ATHENA framework is aimed at giving the possibility to implement those transformations within its consortium of RPOs and RFOs. As it can be observed in Figure 1, **GEPI Committees will act as connections between ATHENA’s team in each RPO/RFO and the rest of the institutional community.**

Figure 1. ATHENA framework for institutional change

Therefore, the main objective of the GEPI Committees is to facilitate the institutional change towards gender equality. This will be achieved by **continuously supporting the development and implementation of the tailored institutional GEP.**

To do so, the ATHENA GEPI Committees are involved in a participatory process and capacity building activities, which will let them raise their awareness and make them familiar with the principles of gender equity and the new practices to be introduced under the project activities. Specifically, Table 1 details the tasks to be performed by the ATHENA GEPI Committees throughout the project.

Table 1. Tasks to be performed by the ATHENA GEPI Committees

Task No.	Task
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Task 1	Support and monitor the implementation of the tailored GEPs within their institutions. For this purpose, the GEPI Committee will meet face-to-face or online in accordance with the indications of the GEPI Committee Chair.
Task 2	Participate in the focus groups organized under WP2 and by each ATHENA RPO/RFO implementing a GEP (T2.3).
Task 3	Receive three trainings: Two online common trainings and a third tailored training specific to each ATHENA institution.
Task 4	Design and deploy a training programme in collaboration with the respective ATHENA partner and the gender expert for the internal organisational staff (T3.3 of the ATHENA work plan).
Task 5	Representatives of the GEPI Committees will attend to three ATHENA mutual learning workshops (T3.4 of the ATHENA work plan).
Task 6	Bilateral talks - Receive assistance from the gender expert for the drafting of the GEP (T4.4 of the ATHENA work plan).
Task 7	Selected representatives of the GEPI Committees will actively participate in the forum of the ATHENA e-platform by answering the questions of participants.
Task 8	Disseminate the action (the ATHENA project and the relevance to strive towards gender equality) through the institutional community and external stakeholders.

As detailed within Table 1 and under task 3.2 of WP3, capacity building activities were implemented, in which the ATHENA GEPI Committees participated in a **training programme aiming at becoming them more aware of the relevance of gender in their work and to help them identify and leverage the appropriate tools and resources to implement the gender strategies** within their institution. Further information on the training programme may be found within section 3.

2.2 Composition of the GEPI Committees

GEPI Committees were established in July 2021 at each ATHENA institution implementing a GEP: JSI, UJK, UB, ULPGC, UVSK SAV, URAK, ACIISI and FRCT. The GEPI Committees include **representatives of each of the ATHENA target groups, being these: 1) high and middle management; 2) HR professionals; 3) Researchers and professors; and 4) Administrative staff**. Students were in some institutions involved on a voluntary basis, being represented by the participation of representatives of student councils/assemblies. ATHENA institutions were invited to include within their Committees the highest number of participants so their quality and

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robustness could be improved and at the same time to compensate eventual drop offs. In addition, to achieve a successful, strategical and sustainable implementation of the GEPs, ATHENA institutions were encouraged to involve within the Committees **institutional members in powerful and relevant positions committed to gender equality**.

Each Committee includes a Chair responsible for coordinating the Committee and its tasks and reporting to the respective project partner.

A total of **92 project GEPI Committee members** were identified. Each member signed a letter of commitment to the project and an informed consent form for the management and treatment of their personal data. Figure 2 displays the distribution of the GEPI Committee members for each ATHENA institution and Annex I – List of the ATHENA GEPI Committee members lists them by their name, surname and position.

Figure 2. Distribution of the ATHENA GEPI Committee members per institution

3. The training programme for the ATHENA GEPI Committees

Implementing gender mainstreaming towards gender equality at RPOs and RFOs is a continuous and long-term process that involve a wide set of tools, instruments and strategies. Trainings towards gender equality is one of these instruments that should be implemented to achieve institutional transformation by building knowledge, raising consciousness, learning empowerment and developing skills.

The **training programme for the ATHENA GEPI Committees** was designed to **boost the gender equality skills of the GEPI Committees members, providing**

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them with the knowledge, skills and values to contribute to the effective implementation of gender strategies in their institution through the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). To achieve gender equality, it is essential that individual staff members are equipped with the understanding and tools that will enable them to properly perform their gender-mainstreaming duties.

3.1 Objective of the training programme

The aim of the capacity building is to **make GEPI Committees more aware of the relevance of gender in their work and to help them identify and leverage the appropriate tools and resources to implement the gender strategies within their institution.**

The trainings provided ATHENA GEPI Committees members with knowledge, competences and skills to promote the institutional systemic change. Skilled GEPI Committee members will then be involved in the design and delivery of training and capacity building activities for the rest of the staff in their organizations (T3.3).

3.2 Structure of the training programme

The training programme was structured into **three trainings**: Two online common trainings devoted to all the ATHENA GEPI Committees and a specific tailored training for each ATHENA institution. **The two first online common trainings were delivered online via the ATHENA e-platform (www.gender-equality.eu).** Prior to the development of these trainings, GEPI Committee members were asked to answer a specific questionnaire aimed at assessing their needs and expectations. The results obtained allowed to set specific topics and content of the common trainings, which addressed the topics 'Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management' and 'ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)' (see Table 2 and Table 3, respectively).

Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L. (CE) was in charge of developing and delivering the two common trainings, which had a **blended format: Trainings 1 and 2 were carried out lively on 19th and 26th November 2021, respectively, via the ATHENA e-platform. Those participants who were not able to join the live sessions took the lessons in a self-paced mode through the e-platform as well.** The live online sessions were given in English.

A third training was specific and tailored to each ATHENA RPO/RFO needs. Each ATHENA institution decided the topic of this training based on the WP2 results, i.e. gender audit (T2.1), organisational assessment (T2.1 and T2.2) and results from the identification of existing gender bias (staff surveys (T2.3.1), storytelling interviews

(T2.3.2) and focus groups (T2.3.3). Specifically, the focus groups were key to discuss on the content of the tailored trainings. ATHENA institutions were provided a non-exhaustive list of potential topics for these tailored trainings so they could be supported with a first battery of themes. ATHENA institutions were invited to adapt the list and/or propose any other topic/s based on their WP2 organisational assessment. This third training was intended to be delivered physically but many of the partners delivered it online due to COVID restrictions.

The content of the three trainings was adapted to each ATHENA type of members of the GEPI Committees: high and middle management, HR professionals, researchers and professors and administrative staff.

Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 display the main characteristics of each of the three trainings.

Table 2. Training 1 - Common training to be delivered to all the ATHENA RPOs/RFOs implementing a GEP

Topic	Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Understand the main concepts of gender equality in research (rationale, legislation and policies, cases of gender (in)equalities tangible and intangible benefits for research organizations.) ▪ Familiarize with the concepts of institutional change and learn on change management practices. ▪ Acquire skills to promote and lead change management (identify and activate key resources and key individuals, engage stakeholders, communicate, monitor and measure) ▪ Learn on main difficulties in change management for gender equalities. ▪ Learn from good practices on change management for gender equalities.
Modality	<p>Online:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live session via Zoom • Self-pace mode via the ATHENA e-platform for those who were not able to attend the live session.
Format	Online course followed by video presentations and virtual activities
Developed and delivered by	Developed by Consulta Europa (CE)

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Duration	4 hours (2 hours online video + 2 hours of remote study – readings and videos of third parties)
Language	Trainings were delivered in English. Partners who needed it translated the PPT presentation and material into their national language.

Table 3. Training 2 – Common training to be delivered to all the ATHENA RPOs/RFOs implementing a GEP

Topic	ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduce the ATHENA context and approach to pursue gender equality ▪ Present the EU legislative framework and policy initiatives for Gender Equality and Gender Equality in Research. ▪ Highlight the relevance of implementing a Gender Equality Plan and outline its implementation process. ▪ Examine a Gender Equality Plan case study
Modality	<p>Online:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live session via Zoom • Self-pace mode via the ATHENA e-platform for those who were not able to attend the live session.
Format	Online course followed by video presentations and virtual activities
Developed and delivered by	Developed by Consulta Europa (CE)
Duration	4 hours (2 hours online video + 2 hours of remote study – readings and videos of third parties)
Language	Trainings were delivered in English. Partners who needed it translated the PPT presentation and material into their national language.

Table 4. Training 3 – Tailored training for each ATHENA RPO/RFO

Topic	Determined by each ATHENA RPO/RFO based on WP2 results
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Objectives	Identified by each ATHENA RPO/RFO based on the selected topic.
Modality	Primarily face-to-face. Partners who were not able to carry out a face-to-face event organized a virtual one.
Format	Classroom lesson
Developed and delivered by	Gender experts at each ATHENA RPO/RFO
Duration	8 hours (2 teaching hours for each ATHENA target group (High and middle managers; HR professionals; professor and researchers; and administrative staff)).
Language	ATHENA national languages

The following sections detail further information on the implementation of the three trainings as well as their programme and material.

3.3 Training 1 – ‘Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management’

The first training of the training programme was entitled ‘**Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management**’ and was carried out live on 19th November 2021 via the ATHENA e-platform. Michelle Perello, CEO of Consulta Europa (CE) and the ATHENA Coordinator, delivered the training in conjunction with invited gender experts.

The material of this training was developed following a consultative process. A pre-training questionnaire was distributed among the GEPI Committees identified so far, so their needs and expectations could be assessed and the training could be designed accordingly. A training proposal was first designed and sent to the project consortium for review. Comments were incorporated and the final version of the material was finally uploaded to the project e-platform.

57 GEPI Committee members registered to the training. It is worth noting that at the time in which the registration form was launched only 75 GEPI Committee members were identified so far. This means a success rate of participation of 76%.

Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the live session of this training.

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Grabando... Usted está viendo la pantalla de Michelle Perello | ATHENA Coor... Ver Opciones Vista

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender stereotypes (I)

Ideas, views or preconceptions whereby females and males are arbitrarily assigned characteristics and roles determined and limited by their gender.

Feminine	Masculine
Soft and caring	Strong and aggressive
Emotional	No emotions
Dependent	Independent
Easily influenced	Not easily influenced
Submissive	Dominant
Talkative	Not at all talkative
Afraid & delicate	Brave & heroic
Sensitive to other's feelings	Less sensitive to other's feelings
Verbal	Analytical
Tactful	Blunt
Indecisive	Decisive
Home-oriented	Worldly

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Figure 3. Screenshot of the live session of the Training 1 - Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

The event agenda may be found at Annex II.a – Material of the common Training/Lecture 1 – Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management. As it may be seen and as above mentioned, two external gender experts were invited to share their experiences on institutional change management. These experts were Jennifer Dahmen-Adkins, from the RWTH Aachen University, member of the H2020 projects LeTSGEPs and CHANGE, and Thomas Berghoefler, from Deutsches Electronen Synchrotron (DESY) and coordinator of the H2020 project GENERA and the GENERA Network. At the end of the event, there was room for open discussion on the main clarifications/highlights/comments/concerns raised by the participants.

The live session was recorded and uploaded at the ATHENA e-platform so GEPI Committee members who were not able to attend the live session could follow the course remotely. The course and the related material are also publicly available at the project e-platform for any person interested in taking the training.

As mentioned in the previous section, the training lasted 4 hours: 2 hours of live session or online video for those who took the lesson through the project e-platform and 2 hours of remote study. The remote study was implemented by worksheets, which were uploaded at the e-platform. GEPI Committee members were requested to complete them by downloading, filling out offline and uploading them to the e-platform. The worksheets, which may be also consulted at Annex II.a – Material of the common Training/Lecture 1 – Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change

management, were adapted to each ATHENA target group (high and middle managers; HR professionals; researchers and professors; and administrative staff).

3.4 Training 2 – ‘ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)’

This second common training was organized lively on November 26th 2021 via the project e-platform. The training, entitled ‘**ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)**’ was delivered by Michelle Perello (CE) in conjunction with invited gender experts.

As for the first training, the material of this second training was prepared following a consultative process to the GEPI Committee members and the project consortium. An assessment questionnaire was distributed among the GEPI Committee members to assess their needs and expectations and design the content of the material accordingly. A first proposal was sent to the consortium for comments and the final version was finally uploaded at the project e-platform.

A total of **60 GEPI Committee registered to this training**. As for the case of the first training, at the time of registration there were 75 GEPI Committee members identified, which supposed a successful participation rate of 80%.

Figure 4 shows a screenshot taken during the live session of this second training.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the live session of the Training 2 – ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

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The agenda, material and adapted worksheets to each ATHENA target group of this training may be consulted at Annex II.b – Material of the common Training/Lecture 2 – ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The event counted with the participation of two external speakers from sister projects that already implemented their GEPs: Ana Belén Amil, Gender Equality Officer from the Centre European University (CEU), and Sara Aguirre-Sánchez-Beato, a gender and diversity expert at the Université Libre de Bruxelles. As for the first training, at the end of this training was also a twenty minutes-slot to discuss on the doubts and comments raised.

The live session of this training is also shared publicly at the project e-platform, as well as the main presentation and related material.

3.5 List of the material developed for the common Trainings 1 and 2

As a summary of what has been commented in the previous sections, this section list all the material developed for each of the two common trainings developed via the project e-platform:

- Main PPT presentation.
- Live session carried out online and its recording uploaded at the project e-platform.
- Worksheets adapted to each ATHENA target groups (high and middle managers; researchers and professors; administrative staff and HR professionals).
- Evaluation form.

The above-listed material is already uploaded on the ATHENA e-platform (www.gender-equality.eu). To access the content of the trainings, interested people should be previously registered. To do so, the 'Register' button at the top right section of the home of the site may be found and the further instructions given should be followed.

As mentioned within tables 2 and 3, project partners were given the possibility of translating the material into their national languages. The project partner ACISI translated the material into Spanish. The translated material is publicly available at the project e-platform.

Figures 5 and 6 show screenshots on how to access the trainings at the project e-platform.

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Figure 5. How to access the trainings section at the ATHENA e-platform

Figure 6. Image 3. How to access the trainings (lectures) of the ATHENA training for GEPI Committees

3.6 Satisfaction assessment of the common Trainings 1 and 2

Once the GEPI Committee members completed the training and its activities, they were requested to answer an evaluation form to gather their impressions, feelings and comments about the two aspects common trainings. A screenshot showing the evaluation form may be found in Annex III – Evaluation form of the trainings 1 and 2 carried out via the ATHENA e-platform. A total of 33 participants answered the evaluation form. Graphics showing the results of the main first three questions are displayed in Figure 7, Figure 8 Figure 9.

Figure 7. Satisfaction assessment - Participants' rating on the online experience

As it may be observed in Figure 7, 50% of respondents were very satisfied with the online experience of the training programme on the e-platform. 30% of respondents stated to be satisfied with the online experience, followed by a 20% who answered to be neutral. No respondents stated to be dissatisfied neither very dissatisfied.

Figure 8. Satisfaction assessment - Participants' rating on the training activity

Figure 8 shows the satisfaction results on to what extent the respondents state the activity exceed, met or did not meet their expectations. 85% of respondents confirmed that the training activity met their expectations, followed by a 15% of respondents who stated that the activity exceeded their expectations. No respondents stated that the training activity did not meet their expectations.

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Figure 9. Satisfaction assessment - To what extent the content of the modules met participants' expectations

Question 3 of the evaluation form asked participants on the extent they considered the contents of the modules meet the objectives planned. As it can be observed in Figure 9, 45% of respondents stated that the content of the modules fully met the objectives, followed by a 35% who rated the question with a value of 4 within the Likert scale. No respondents stated that the objectives of the modules did not meet the objectives pursued.

3.7 Specific tailored trainings to each ATHENA institution

Each ATHENA institution implementing the GEPs designed, developed and delivered a specific tailored training to their GEPI Committee members. The trainings were developed by the subcontracted gender experts in conjunction with the project partners and delivered by the gender experts. The topics of the trainings were selected from the evaluation of the strengths and weaknesses of the gender situation at each ATHENA institution, based on the results obtained from WP2 activities, especially from the results of the focus groups. It was necessary to identify what changes were expected and what it wanted to be achieved through the trainings, and WP2 results provided ATHENA institutions with information on the areas where action was most needed.

ATHENA partners agreed with their gender experts on the most appropriate content, tools and techniques used based on their needs. They were requested to fill in a proposal template to inform the coordinator of the activity and the rest of the consortium on the programme and schedule.

ATHENA institutions were also requested to adapt the tailored training to each ATHENA target group. The tailored trainings had a duration of around 8 hours of teaching lessons. These trainings for the GEPI Committees were a ‘train the trainers’ activity, which pursued to qualify the members of the Committees for them to later deploy a gender training programme to the internal institutional staff (T3.3). Thus, when working on the content of the trainings and delivering those, partners were requested to include facilitation exercises/techniques/methods to support on the promotion of the content to the rest of the institutional community.

All materials included the ATHENA visual identity and the acknowledgement to the European Commission (EC), as stated in Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement (GA). In addition, the gender experts that delivered the trainings were requested to sign an informed consent form so the recording of the trainings may be uploaded on the ATHENA e-platform.

For each specific tailored training, the following information from the ATHENA institutions was compiled:

- Training proposal informing about the event outline and agenda.
- Attendees list.
- Recording of the trainings (to be uploaded to the project e-platform).
- Reporting template.

Templates for the training proposal and event reporting may be consulted within Annex IV – Templates for the specific tailored trainings.

The Table 5 below presents the topics and schedule of the specific tailored trainings carried out at each ATHENA institution.

Table 5. Specific tailored trainings for each ATHENA institution - Event schedule

ATHENA institution	Topic of tailored training	Date(s) of delivery of the training	Modality
JSI	How to resist gender bias in an academic field	14 January 2022	Online
UJK	1. Design, Implementation, Monitoring and Evaluation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) 2. Unconscious bias 3. Tools for an inclusive communication	1. 30 November and 1 December 2021 2. 16 December 2021 3. 16 December 2021	Physically
UB	Transformative leadership for	12 and 13 January	Online

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	Gender Equality in the University	2022	
ULPGC	Tackling work-life balance and gender-based and sexual harassment and violence in the university context	20 and 21 January 2022	Online
UVSK SAV	Gender equality in everyday life of the institution	16 December 2021	Online
URAK	Local gender equality legislation and anti-discrimination practices	3 and 10 December 2021	Online
GOBCAN	Introduction to gender equality mainstreaming and gender equality plans	1 and 2 December 2021	Online
FRCT	Tools for an inclusive Portuguese language	19 and 21 January 2022	Physically and online

Annex I – List of the ATHENA GEPI Committee members

ATHENA institution: **Jozef Stefan Institute (JSI)**

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Barbara Malic	Head of department K5
GEPI members	Miha Cekada	Head of department F3
	Ita Junkar	Researcher at F4 department
	Sasa Novak Krmpotic	Researcher at K7 department
	Miha Cekada	Head of department F3
	Ita Junkar	Researcher at F4 department
	Sasa Novak Krmpotic	Researcher at K7 department
	Spelar Stres	Head of Center for Technology Transfer and Innovation at JSI
	Mojca Otonicar	Researcher at K5 department
	Tamara Kotnik	Head of HR department at JSI
	Luka Virag	Adviser in director's Office at JSI
	Alma Mehle	Assistant to the Advisor to the Director at U1 department
	Pia Staric	Young researcher at F4 department

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	Rok Novak	Young researcher at O2 department
	Marina Santo Zarnik	Researcher and professor group
	Matjaž Koželj	Researcher
	Junoš Lukan	Researcher
	Vesna Butinar	Administrative staff

ATHENA institution: Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce (UJK)

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Ana Kaminska	Professor
GEPI members	Prof. dr hab Marzna Marczevska	Member of University Science Council
	Prof UJK dr hab. Barbara Gawdzik	Deputy Rector for Education
	Dr Magdalena Molendowska	Deputy Dean for Education, Faculty of Law and Social Sciences
	Prof. dr hab. Francesco Giacosa	Director of Doctoral School
	Prof UJK dr hab. Lidia Michalska-Bracha	Deputy Director of Doctoral School
	Dr Joanna Rogalska	Deputy Director for Education of Department of Economics and Finance

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	Dr Rafał Miernik	Assistant Professor
	Dr Justyna Palacz	Head of Education Office
	Beata Banach-Rząca	Head of Head of Department of International Exchange and Cooperation
	Agnieszka Bygar	Head of Science Department

ATHENA institution: **University of Bucharest**

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Mirabela Amarandei	Director, Strategic Governance, Evaluation, Monitoring and Public Policies, University of Bucharest CIVIS Project Manager, Spokesperson
GEPI members	Prof. Carmen Chifiriuc	Vice-rector, Research, director ICUB
	Daniela Popa	Director Human Resources
	Oana Sârbu	Director, General Secretariat
	Associate Prof. Romina Surugiu	Vice-Dean, Faculty of Journalism and Media Communication
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	Isabel Selaru	Training and staff development Office
	Prof. Romiță Iucu	President, Board of Trustee-UB, Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences
	Student Dragoş Obreja	Student, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work

ATHENA institution: University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Francisco Artilles López	Vice Manager of Human Resources
GEPI members	Asunción Beerly Palacio	Vice Rector of Social Projection and Communication
	Inmaculada González Cabrera	General Secretary
	Carmen Grau Pineda	Director of teaching staff
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ATHENA institution: Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Adademie VIED (UVSK SAV)

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	doc. PhDr. Gabriel Bianchi, CSc.	Deputy director
GEPI members	Ing. Ivana Budinská, PhD.	Director
	Mgr. Zuzana Černáková, PhD.	Programme Officer
	prof. RNDr. Ľubica Lacinová, DrSc.	Member of the Presidium of SAS - section 2.
	JUDr. Zuzana Magurová, LL.M.	Researcher
	PhDr. Jana Cviková, PhD.	Gender expert and academic secretary
	RNDr. Šárka Horáčková, PhD.	Researcher, member of the Young researchers of SAS
	prof. RNDr. Silvia Pastoreková, DrSc.	Director
	Mgr. Katarína Bešková, PhD.	Researcher

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	Mgr. Martin Venhart, PhD.,	Vice president for section 1, research scientist, head of department of nuclear physics
	Mgr. Zuzana Panczová, PhD.	Senior research fellow
	Mgr. Róbert Karul, PhD	Member of SAS's presidency and Head of the Commission for Equal Opportunities

ATHENA institution: **University of Ruse Angel Kanchev (URAK)**

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Prof. Dr. Diana Antonova	Director Scientific UNICOMP / Vice-rector Research
GEPI members	Prof. Dr. Vanya Serbezova	Director Quality in education
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Boris Evstatiev	Director Scientific Research Center
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Orlin Petrov	Head of Academic Staff Development
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Galina Ivanova	Head of the PhD School
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Pavlov	Head of the Entrepreneurship Center
	Mrs Yana Kraleva	Chief Accountant
	Mrs Ralitsa Barashka	Legal advisor
	Mrs Lyusi Dimitrova	HR department expert

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	Nataliya Venelinova PhD	Department in Management and Social Affairs
	Mrs Galina Daskalova	Administrative expert in Research
	Mrs Daniela Todorova	Administrative expert in Quality in education

ATHENA institution: **Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society of Regional Government of Canary islands (ACIISI)**

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Antonio López Gulías	Head of area at ACIISI
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	Patricia Oramas Gallar	Head of section
	Domingo Guzmán Palacios Arazuri	Head of section
	Francisco Javier Roo Filgueira	Project manager
	Angeles Varona	Administrative staff

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ATHENA institution: **Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)**

	Name and Surname	Position
GEPI Committee Chair	Gisela Nascimento	Member of the Directive Board of FRTC
GEPI members	Carolina Parelho	Project officer and manager
	Renato Pires	Project officer and manager
	Miguel Vieira	Financial manager
	Marta Bezerra	Financial manager
	Tiago Valente	Project manager
	João Lima	Advanced Training Support Office
	Marisa Silva	Advanced Training Support Office
	Paula Medeiros	Administrative
	Rafael Pereira	Project manager intern

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Annex II – Material of the training programme

Annex II.a – Material of the common Training/Lecture 1 – Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

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Event agenda

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Online Training for GEPI Committees - Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Lecture/Module 1 - Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

AGENDA

Friday, November 19th 2021

Zoom: [Link to connect here](#)

Event Time Zone: 10.30h (CEST Time)

10.30h – 11.30h Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

Michelle Perello - Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L. (CE) – ATHENA Coordinator.

Michelle holds a Ph.D. on social innovation for the Politecnico di Torino. She established Consulta Europa in 2009, a SME specialized in European funds, European project planning and management, territorial development policies and gender consultancy. Michelle has been supporting Spanish companies to develop and implement their gender equality plans. In addition, Michelle has acted as gender Auditor in several H2020 projects like RURITAGE, URBANWASTE or FORWARD. In URBANWASTE she was also responsible of developing strategic gender sensitivity trainings related to the environmental contents addressed by the project. She is the ATHENA project coordinator.

11.30h – 11.50h Micro Change Agency in EU-funded Gender Equality Projects

Jennifer Dahmen-Adkins - RWTH Aachen University.

Jennifer Dahmen-Adkins, graduate social scientist, is a research associate at the Chair of Technology and Organisation at the Institute of Sociology at RWTH Aachen University. Her research focuses on gender and intersectionality research, as well as higher education and organisational research, each with a strong "theory-practice" connection. She is currently responsible for the process monitoring and evaluation of two H2020 projects of the EU Commission, which deal with the institutionalisation of gender equality plans in science and research institutions. In addition, Jennifer Dahmen-Adkins has been appointed as the German representative of the Management Committee of the COST Action 'VOICES'.

11.50h – 12.10h Institutional change towards gender equality - when mission impossible shall be accomplished

Thomas Berghoefer, Deutsches Elektronen Synchrotron (DESY).

Thomas studied Physics and Astrophysics at the universities of Marburg and Bochum, and received his PhD from the Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich. During his active research career he was working in X-ray and EUV astronomy at the Max-Planck-Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics, the Space Sciences Lab of UC Berkeley, and the observatory of University of Hamburg. While working at the University of Hamburg he was appointed as one of the women's representatives in the faculty of physics. Later he became a science programme manager in the German research funding system of the federal government. He was the coordinator of the EU funded H2020 GENERA project and currently coordinates the GENERA Network. One of the aims of the network is to support, coordinate and improve gender equality policies in physics research organisations in Europe and world-wide.

12.10h – 12.30 h Open discussion

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Main presentation

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course

November 2021

Module 1 Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

Content

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality
2. Main policies for Gender Equality
3. Gender equality in research and academia
4. Institutional change

2

Introductory concepts

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender and sex

Sex

Biologically-defined and genetically acquired differences between females and males, in accordance with their physiology and reproductive capabilities or potentialities.

Gender

Social characteristics associated with being a woman or a man. These include the economic, social, political, and cultural attributes and opportunities, as well as the roles and responsibilities associated with being woman or a man.

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1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender and sex: Differences

Sex

- It is **universal and mostly unchanging** (changing with surgery).
- **Identify 'females' and 'males' independently** of each other.
- **Do not vary** over time and geographically.

Gender

- Gender is **socially constructed**, constituted differently across the world and changes over time.
- **Identify 'females' and 'males'** based on the **socio-cultural relationships** between them.
- Gender **varies over time and geographically**.

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1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender roles

Gender roles are **behaviors, attitudes, tasks and responsibilities** that are considered **acceptable and appropriate** for females and males as **consequence of socio-cultural norms and beliefs**. They are usually **learned in childhood** and may **vary over time** as a result of **social and/or political changes**.

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1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender stereotypes (I)

Ideas, views or preconceptions whereby females and males are **arbitrarily assigned characteristics** and roles **determined and limited by their gender**.

Feminine

Soft and caring
Emotional
Dependent
Easily influenced
Submissive
Talkative
Afraid & delicate
Sensitive to other's feelings
Verbal
Tactful
Indecisive
Home-oriented

Masculine

Strong and aggressive
No emotions
Independent
Not easily influenced
Dominant
Not at all talkative
Brave & heroic
Less sensitive to other's feelings
Analytical
Blunt
Decisive
Worldly

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1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender stereotypes (II)

*'Gender stereotyping can **limit the development of the natural talents and abilities** of girls and boys, women and men, as well as their **educational and professional experiences and life opportunities** in general. Stereotypes about women both result from, and are the cause of, deeply **engrained attitudes, values, norms and prejudices** against women. They **are used to justify and maintain the historical relations of power of men over women** as well as **sexist attitudes that hold back the advancement of women.**'*

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EIGE 2021

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender equality vs Gender equity

Gender equity

Fairness in participation, representation and benefits.

Gender equity means that females and males have an **impartial and unbiased chance of having their needs met** and each may **equally access to opportunities for realizing their full potential.**

Gender equality

Equal opportunity for females and males to **access and use resources and services** within families, communities and society.

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender awareness

The understanding that there are **differences between women and men that are determined socially by learned behavior and that affect their ability to access and control resources.**

Gender awareness raising

(EIGE 2021) Gender awareness raising aims to **promote and encourage a general understanding of gender-related challenges**, for instance, violence against women and the gender pay gap, among others. It also aims to **show how values and norms influence our reality, reinforce stereotypes and support the structures that produce inequalities.**

Gender awareness raising plays an important role in informing women and men about gender equality, the benefits of a more gender-equal society and the consequences of gender inequality.

1. Introductory concepts to gender equality

Gender analysis

The EU Commission defines gender analysis as *'the study of differences in the conditions, needs, participation rates, access to resources and development, control of assets, decision-making powers, etc., between women and men in their assigned gender roles'*.

Gender analysis provides disaggregated data by sex, and an understanding of the social construction of the gender roles, how labour is divided and valued.

Thus, gender analysis is **necessary to integrate a gender perspective into policies, programmes and projects.**

2. Main policies for Gender Equality

Gender equality

Key priority in Member States and European institutions

- Art. 2 and 3 of [Treaty on European Union](#) and Art. 8 of [Treaty on Functioning of EU](#)
- Art. 23 of [Charter of Fundamental Rights](#)
- Principles 2 and 9 of the [European Pillar of Social Rights](#)
- [Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action](#) (4th World Conference on Women, 1995)
- [UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development \(Goal 5\)](#)
- [EU gender equality strategy 2020-2025](#)
- [Action Plan on Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in External Action 2021-2025 \(GAP III\)](#)

2. Main policies for Gender Equality

EU Framework & Policies: Timeline

3. Gender equality in research and academia

Relevance of gender in research and academia

3. Gender equality in research and academia

Relevance of gender in research and academia

3. Gender equality in research and academia

EU Framework & Policies 2021-2027

The EU, and more specifically the European Commission are **strongly committed to promoting gender equality in research and innovation.**

3. Gender equality in research and academia

EU Framework & Policies 2021-2027

Communication on the ERA (2020)

- **Common action between EU countries to strengthen gender equality provisions.**
- Action 12 invites EU countries to **develop concrete plans to promote gender equality.**
- In conjunction with the Skills Agenda and the new Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027 also pursues to **reinforce an increasing participation of women in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).**

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Relevance of gender in research and academia

Reasons and mechanisms that keep women away from research and from moving up the career ladder

- **Gender discriminatory practices: Biased recruitment, promotion and funding processes and criteria.** Gender discrimination may operate in highly formalized and seemingly gender-neutral peer-review processes or selection and promotion procedures.

Forms of gender discrimination in science

- **Gender stereotypes in science.**

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

- Gender segregation in research and science
- Gender-related career challenges
- Gender imbalance in senior positions in academia
- Gender bias in access to research funding
- Gender-blind and gender-biased research
- Gender-blind and gender-biased organisational culture and institutional process

EIGE 2021

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender segregation in research

Gender segregation in research is driven by:

- Gender stereotypes
- Choice of study field
- Gender division of labour
- Time constraints
- Covert barriers and biases in organisation practices

(SHE Figures 2021) Despite the gap between women and men in doctoral degrees has narrowed (women make up 48%), **women remains under-represented in ICT professions**, making up only 24.9% of self-employed professionals.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender-related career challenges

A **smaller proportion of women** moves up the **educational/professional hierarchy**.

At each transition step from an educational/professional stage to another within the science path, more women are **loosen**.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender imbalance in senior positions in academia

- Women face a **glass ceiling** when moving to higher positions.
- (*She Figures 2018*) Women the **proportion of women was the smallest at the top of the academic hierarchy** (20% of Grade A academic staff; 37% Grade B; and 44% Grade C).
- (*She Figures 2018*) **Only 10% of EU Universities/research institutions are headed by a woman** rector.

(*She Figures 2021*) Women are still under-represented in senior academic positions (accounting for 42.3% of the academic staff, with 26.2% corresponding to Tier 1 academic positions), as well as in key decision-making positions (23.6% of heads of HEIs).

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender bias in access to research funding

Common trends (EIGE's gender in research report):

- Missed monitoring** of the gender of the applicants and awardees.
- The great majority of members of boards, committees and evaluation panels** in many countries **are men**. Orientation, priorities and gender equality policies of the RFOs may be influenced and the lack of women in boards may give image of a system that does not welcome women.
- The recruitment of peer reviews** often remains opaque and gender is only rarely mentioned among the **evaluation criteria**.
- There is **little research on application** behaviour and especially on its **gender patterns**.

(*She Figures 2021*) Women continues being **less successful than men in securing research funding (-3.9%) and in holding patents (10.7% of patent holders are women)**.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender-blind and gender-biased research

- Recognising and **considering the differences between sex and gender** is key for the **creation of new scientific knowledge**.
- Much **research is still gender blind or gender biased**.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Persistent gender inequalities

Gender-blind and gender-biased organisational culture and institutional process

- **Most of the decision-making procedures** at RPOs and RFOS were established at a time in which there was **limited presence and impact of women**.
- The **inclusion of gender analysis in research** can lead to **innovation, full use of talent, an increase in the quality of the scientific research** as well as an **appeal for scientific careers**.

To achieve positive changes in gender at RPOs/RFOS is necessary to create gender-friendly environments: allocation of resources, arrangement of working hours and contracts, and face intra-organisational rivalries that characterise all organisations.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Benefits of achieving gender equality

Results of the institution

- **More market opportunities** may be found if sex and gender differences are considered and if the different impacts related to gender are distinguished.
- **New perspectives, questions and areas of research** are offered by integrating sex and gender analysis into research.
- **Greater focus on results and effects.** Taking gender analysis into consideration as well as knowledge on gender issues in the planning stages requires a research-based approach towards thinking and acting.
- **Better quality of the services provided and better governance**, as result of that considering gender mainstreaming triggers evidence-based decision making.
- **Better legitimize policies** as the needs and interests of women and men are considered.

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3. Gender equality in research and academia

Benefits of achieving gender equality

Staff management

- **Better performance of the institution:** the promotion of women and men based on their talents and not on the ground of their sex will help the achievement of better results.
- **Contribution to employee satisfaction** as unfair disadvantages for staff members are limited.
- Measure to improve work life balance of staff can contribute to a **decrease of staff expenses** in the long-term because of improved employee health.
- Equal opportunities policies can contribute to higher levels of **internal and external credibility and better public image**.
- The abovementioned can therefore contribute to making **the institution more attractive for potential job applicants**.

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4. Institutional change

What is institutional change?

Deep change of an institution also **affecting the outside environment:**

- Changes in the **basic values and beliefs** that are dominant.
- Changes in the **rules and regulations** leading to concrete working results.

Institutional change is a continuous process due to the transforming environment, which create new demands or incentives for transformation.

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4. Institutional change

- How do you feel about change?

'Change is always a threat when done to me, but it is an opportunity when done by me. Many people hate change because it is inflicted on them; someone else is making them do it. Or because circumstances are totally out of their control...On the other hand, people change all the time and love it, because they go after something they want'

Rosabeth Moss Kanter (2015)

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4. Institutional change

Cycle of organisational change for gender equality

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4. Institutional change

Cycle of organisational change for gender equality

Identify the need for change

- Actually, **EU and national governments are triggering institutional change** at research public institutions.
- Internally, **managers must be highly committed and be involved** in the institutional change in:
 - Goals
 - Approaches to planning
 - Encouraging participation
 - Adopting innovations or concepts like quality or equality

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4. Institutional change

Cycle of organisational change for gender equality

Define the opportunity/problem

Are there better options to make the institution more efficient, effective and a satisfactory place to work?

- For example, how far women have progressed within the research/institutional hierarchy? Does it reflect their full potential? Or how new female researchers have been involved in specific department, such as ICT or Engineering (also how new male researchers have been introduced in Education, Nursing, etc.)?

Gender disaggregated data are key to address such type of questions

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4. Institutional change

Cycle of organisational change for gender equality

Evaluate the possible measures to integrate gender equality change

- Which are the possible measures to be adopted to integrate gender equality within the institution?
- Proposed measures should be monitored (e.g. raising the percentage of women in leadership and decision making positions).
- Action plans need to consider what is feasible to implement in the context of the institutional culture.

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4. Institutional change

Cycle of organisational change for gender equality

Implement the change and monitoring

- When implementing and monitoring the action plan, it is important that there is:
 - **Stability** to achieve the current goals.
 - **Continuity** to ensure the orderly change.
 - **Adaptability** to react to new or unexpected threats and opportunities.
 - **Innovativeness** to allow the institution to be proactive and initiate change when required.

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4. Institutional change

Key people involved in driving the change

Top down/ Bottom down support

Make use of teams

Change Agents - Gender Equality Plan (GEPI) Implementation Committee

- Senior managers must be committed to the necessary actions for gender equality.
- It is crucial to stimulate **grass-roots support from those who become change agents** (ATHENA GEPI Committees).
- **Set up a GEP implementation team (ATHENA GEPI Committees).**
 - Shared ownership of the vision
 - Diverse perspectives (gender, age, seniority, academic/professional).
 - Broader engagement
- **GEPI Committees:**
 - Work with the rest of the research community to build a shared vision of gender equality as of utmost importance
 - Include people in strategic positions.
 - Arise from diverse functions (high and middle management; research and professors; HR professionals; administrative staff).

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4. Institutional change

Communicate: Embed gender within the institutional culture

Institutional culture should be in line with the vision of gender equality.

Events should be organized in order to make visible all the aspects of gender as well as to draw attention to gender-related issues.

The language used should be gender-sensitized.

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4. Institutional change

Communicate achievements and successes

Utilize communication channels (website, social media, etc.)

Give rewards and recognition of achievements to all levels.

Organize events (awards, receptions...)

Networking with colleagues (inside and outside the institution)

4. Institutional change

Success factors for institutional change

[EIGE Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans in research and higher education institutions](#)

- Support from leadership and senior management.
- Well-equipped and well-located 'gender equality body'.
- Involvement of different categories of stakeholders.
- Embedding into existing structures and management procedures.
- Availability of sex-disaggregated data.
- Setting clear targets and practical objectives.
- Developing competences.
- Monitoring and evaluation practices.
- Flexibility and resilience.

4. Institutional change

Common obstacles

[EIGE Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans in research and higher education institutions](#)

- Resistance to change
- Absence of dedicated, adequate and sustained resources.
- Lack of a committed institutional authority.
- Academic excellence or promotion on merit alone.
- Limited autonomy for public institutions to enable changes related to gender equality.
- Lack of understanding of the need for and importance of gender equality.
- Lack of availability, or access to, sex-disaggregated human resources data.

4. Institutional change

Fields of actions of change and examples of gender equality measures

Work-life balance

- Childcare places for staff available in local centres.
- Creation of a sexual harassment prevention unit.
- Set up of baby feeding/changing room.
- Introduction of core hours.
- Introduction of family friendly policies.
- Establishment of committee for sexual assault/harassment.
- Inclusive LGBT+ policies.

4. Institutional change

Fields of actions of change and examples of gender equality measures

Career progression

- Reduced teaching time for academics seeking qualification for promotion.
- Career development workshops for students.
- Workshops for senior management.
- Leadership training/peer mentoring for female academics.

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4. Institutional change

Fields of actions of change and examples of gender equality measures

Gender and knowledge

- Creation of a new centre for research and coordination on gender quality.
- Gender courses for under and post-graduates.
- Training on gender in research.
- Integration of gender perspectives into new curriculum.
- Introduction of mandatory gender course.
- Introduction of master degree in gender.
- Workshops on gender violence in fieldwork and management of research teams.
- Training for programme coordinators on gender dimension.
- Research proposal writing workshop for female academics.

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4. Institutional change

Fields of actions of change and examples of gender equality measures

Institutional governance

- Monitoring of gender percentage in selection committees.
- Appointment of women on boards/committees.
- Upgrading of job titles held by women.
- Use of gender-neutral language in communications.
- Training for senior management and administrative staff on gender equality and diversity and unconscious bias.
- Training of HR professionals on data collection on gender.
- Inclusion of gender data in annual reports.
- Inclusion of gender sensitized data in job advertisements.
- New policies on parental leave, sexual harassment.

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Tailored worksheets

- **Register** to the ATHENA e-platform: www.gender-equality.eu
- **Access this training** 'Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe'.
- **Access 'Lecture 1** - Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management'.
- **At the bottom of the page**, you will find the **additional material to be completed offline and that is adapted to each ATHENA target group**.
- **Complete the 'Forced Field Analysis' and worksheet PDF files** and submit them by **uploading the e-platform**.

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Thank you for your attention!

training@gender-equality.eu

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Worksheets

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course worksheet

- Module 1: Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management
- ATHENA target group: [High and middle managers](#)

Once attended the live session or watched the presentation of the module 1 'Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management' of this online course, please utilize this worksheet to complete the online tasks.
You are encouraged to fully complete the tasks to benefit on building your knowledge and experience on institutional change management.

<p>Task 1: Interview 'Gender bias in academia: myth or fact?'</p> <p>Read the interview between Esade Associate Professors Pedro Rey Biel and Ivanka Visnjic, in which they explain why climbing the academic ladder is still harder for women.</p> <p>Access the interview here.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Task 2: Video 'Six keys to leading positive change'</p> <p>Watch the video of Rosabeth Moss Kanter, a leadership expert and Harvard Business School professor, where she uses the stories of great leaders and ordinary people to reveal the six success factors that are key to positive change.</p> <p>Access the video here.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>Task 3: Reflect 'Forced Field Analysis – Kurt Lewin'</p> <p>Watch the video from Howard Bailey about 'Forced Field Analysis', analysis created by Kurt Lewin.</p> <p>Access the video here.</p> <p>After you have watched the video, complete the '<i>Forced Field Analysis</i>' worksheet you can download from the '<i>Lecture files</i>' section. To complete it, you will have to think of an institutional change in your organization (i.e. new policies on parental leave, sexual harassment, policy to use language-neutral language in communications, etc.) and identify forces "for" and "against" change.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Task 4: Read 'Gender stakeholder consultation'

Read the section on 'Gender stakeholder consultation' of the Gender mainstreaming tool of the EIGE's website.

Access the reading [here](#).

Having read the EIGE's section, please complete the following questions:

- Identify a basic problem, challenge, opportunity or issue of your competence and that you think it should be addressed in your institution.
- Identify the stakeholders' groups that would be involved in the consultation process.
- Think about and shortly describe one appropriate participatory process to solve the problem, challenge, opportunity or issue.
- Can you think of any other example of useful stakeholder engagement tools in addition to those cited in the article?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 5: Video 'Why we have too few women leaders' & Case study - The new election procedure for the Board of Ghent University

1. Watch the video 'Why we have too few women leaders', where Facebook COO Sheryl Sandberg looks at why a smaller percentage of women than men reach the top of their professions.

Access the video [here](#).

2. Read the good practice from the EIGE's website on the new election procedure for the Board of Ghent University.

Access the good practice [here](#).

After you have read the good practice, please answer the following questions:

- a) Please, detail what are your initial thoughts and reaction to the reading.

- b) Can you think of any other examples/measures to increase the number of women at leadership and decision-making positions?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course worksheet

- Module 1: Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management
- ATHENA target group: [Researchers and professors](#)

Once attended the live session or watched the presentation of the module 1 'Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management' of this online course, please utilize this worksheet to complete the online tasks.
You are encouraged to fully complete the tasks to benefit on building your knowledge and experience on institutional change management.

<p>Task 1: Interview 'Gender bias in academia: myth or fact?'</p> <p>Read the interview between Esade Associate Professors Pedro Rey Biel and Ivanka Visnjic, in which they explain why climbing the academic ladder is still harder for women.</p> <p>Access the interview here.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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<p>Task 3: Reflect 'Forced Field Analysis – Kurt Lewin'</p> <p>Watch the video from Howard Bailey about 'Forced Field Analysis', analysis created by Kurt Lewin.</p> <p>Access the video here.</p> <p>After you have watched the video, complete the 'Forced Field Analysis' worksheet you can download from the 'Lecture files' section. To complete it, you will have to think of an institutional change in your organization (i.e. creation of a new centre for research on gender equality, integration of gender perspectives into new curriculum, etc.) and identify forces "for" and "against" change.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Task 4: Read 'Gender stakeholder consultation'

Read the section on 'Gender stakeholder consultation' of the Gender mainstreaming tool of the EIGE's website.

Access the reading [here](#).

Having read the EIGE's section, please complete the following questions:

- Identify a basic problem, challenge, opportunity or issue that directly affects you as a researcher and that you think it should be addressed in your institution.
- Identify the stakeholders' groups that would be involved in the consultation process.
- Think about one appropriate participatory process to solve the problem, challenge, opportunity or issue.
- Can you think of any other examples of useful stakeholder engagement tools in addition to those cited in the article?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 5: Case studies: How the consideration of sex and gender analysis may create gendered innovations.

1. Go through the Gendered Innovations website (access [here](#)) and select an example of research close to your field.
2. Read how the gender sensitive approach has been included within the research.
3. Search on the internet in non-academic resources of the research selected and check if they mention gender.

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course worksheet

- Module 1: Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management
- ATHENA target group: [Human resources \(HR\) professionals](#)

Once attended the live session or watched the presentation of the module 1 'Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management' of this online course, please utilize this worksheet to complete the online tasks.

You are encouraged to fully complete the tasks to benefit on building your knowledge and experience on institutional change management.

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Task 4: Read 'Gender stakeholder consultation'

Read the section on 'Gender stakeholder consultation' of the Gender mainstreaming tool of the EIGE's website.

Access the read [here](#).

Having read the EIGE's section, please complete the following questions:

- Identify a basic problem, challenge, opportunity or issue that directly affects you as part of the HR unit of your institution and that you think it should be addressed.
- Identify the stakeholders' groups that would be involved in the consultation process.
- Think about one appropriate participatory process to solve the problem, challenge, opportunity or issue.
- Can you think of any other examples of useful stakeholder engagement tools in addition to those cited in the article?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 5: Video 'Unconscious bias: Stereotypical hiring practices' & reading 'How to avoid gender bias in job postings'.

1. Watch the video 'Unconscious bias: Stereotypical hiring practices', where Gail Tolstoi-Miller, as recruiter and career coach, shares her personal story of bias.

Access the video [here](#).

2. Read the article from 'The Conversation' on 'How to avoid gender bias in job postings'.

Access the reading [here](#).

3. After you have watched the video and read the article, answer the following questions:

- a) What are your initial thoughts and reactions to the video?

- b) Can you think of examples of unconscious bias in recruitment from your own experience?

- c) Apart from those detailed in the article of 'The Conversation', may you propose other examples of initiatives to avoid gender bias in recruitment?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course worksheet

- Module 1: Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management
- ATHENA target group: Administrative staff

Once attended the live session or watched the presentation of the module 1 'Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management' of this online course, please utilize this worksheet to complete the online tasks.
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<p>Task 1: Interview 'Gender bias in academia: myth or fact?'</p> <p>Read the interview between Esade Associate Professors Pedro Rey Biel and Ivanka Visnjic, in which they explain why climbing the academic ladder is still harder for women.</p> <p>Access the interview here.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Access the read [here](#).

Having read the EIGE's section, please complete the following questions:

a) Identify a basic problem, challenge, opportunity or issue that directly affects you as part of the administrative unit of your institution and that you think it should be addressed.

b) Identify the stakeholders' groups that would be involved in the consultation process.

c) Think about one appropriate participatory process to solve the problem, challenge, opportunity or issue.

d) Can you think of any other examples of useful stakeholder engagement tools in addition to those cited in the article?

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 5: Reading 'Gender statistics and indicators'

Read the EIGE's section on 'Gender statistics and indicators' on how to integrate a gender perspective into statistical data.

Access the reading [here](#).

Forced Field Analysis Worksheet

Forces FOR change	Score
Total	

Change proposal

Forces AGAINST change	Score
Total	

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Annex II.b – Material of the common Training/Lecture 2 – ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

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Event agenda

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Online Training for GEPI Committees - Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Lecture/Module 2 – ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans

AGENDA

Friday, November 26th 2021

Zoom: Link to connect [here](#)

Event Time Zone: 10.30h (CEST Time)

10.30h – 11.25h Gender equality: Introductory concepts and institutional change management

Michelle Perello - Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L. (CE) – ATHENA Coordinator.

Michelle holds a Ph.D. on social innovation for the Politecnico di Torino. She established Consulta Europa in 2009, a SME specialized in European funds, European project planning and management, territorial development policies and gender consultancy. Michelle has been supporting Spanish companies to develop and implement their gender equality plans. In addition, Michelle has acted as gender Auditor in several H2020 projects like RURITAGE, URBANWASTE or FORWARD. In URBANWASTE she was also responsible of developing strategic gender sensitivity trainings related to the environmental contents addressed by the project. She is the ATHENA project coordinator.

11.25h – 11.40h Break

11.40h – 11.55h Designing and implementing GEPs in Higher Education. The case of Central European University

Ana Belén Amil – Centre European University (CEU).

Ana Belén Amil is the Gender Equality Officer of Central European University for the EU-funded [SUPERA Project](#) (*Supporting the Promotion of Equality in Research and Academia*). As such, her main role is to coordinate the design, implementation and monitoring of CEU's first Gender Equality Plan. She has also developed training scripts and delivered gender equality trainings for another EU-funded project, [GE Academy](#), aimed at developing and implementing a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in research, innovation and higher education. Ana Belén holds an Erasmus Mundus 2-year MA degree in Women's and Gender Studies ([GEMMA](#)) from Central European University and University of Oviedo. She is a clinical psychologist graduated at the University of Buenos Aires. Before becoming CEU's gender equality officer, she worked at the [Human Rights Initiative](#) (HRSI) at CEU as a Project Manager.

11.55h – 12.10h Challenges and opportunities for the design of a Gender Equality Plan in STEM: experiences from ULB within the CALIPER project

Sara Aguirre-Sánchez-Beato, Université libre de Bruxelles.

Sara Aguirre is a gender and diversity expert at the *Université libre de Bruxelles* (ULB). She holds a master's degree in gender studies and a PhD in psychology. In her doctoral thesis, she explored the discursive construction of normative gender categories in the law and in the workplace, focusing on the effects of exclusion on trans* people. As a scholar, she is particularly interested in understanding inequalities, exclusion, and discrimination through the lens of everyday social and institutional practices. She currently works as a post-doc researcher and project manager within the [ULB Gender & Diversity Plan](#) and the [CALIPER](#) project, a European project aiming at fostering gender equality in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Within the framework of this project, she managed the gender analysis and the design of the Gender Equality Plan at ULB.

12.10h – 12.30 h Open discussion

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Main presentation

Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course

November 2021

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Module 2

ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

1

Module 2 ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

Content

1. What is ATHENA?
2. ATHENA context to pursue gender equality (GE)
3. EU policies and initiatives for institutional change and GEPs
4. Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in RPOs and RFOs

2

ATHENA project

1. What is ATHENA?

Programme	H2020
Programme acronym	H2020-SwafS-2020
Contract type	H2020-CSA
Grant Agreement	101006416
Start date of project	1 February 2021
Duration	48 months
Budget	1,828,310.00€

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1. What is ATHENA?

Overall objective

Support consortium partners, which include 6 Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and 2 Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), in the **development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** as a way to generate **systemic institutional changes**.

1. What is ATHENA?

Consortium

Central-Eastern Europe and outermost regions territories

Among the lowest gender equality indexes (GEI) in Europe

Partner No.	Partner organisation name	Acronym	Type of organization	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	SME	ES
2	Jozef Stefan Institute	JSI	RPO	SL
3	Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce	UJK	RPO	PL
4	University of Bucharest	UB	RPO	RO
5	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC	RPO	ES
6	National Research Council. Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies	CNR	RFO	IT
7	Ustav Vyskumu Sociálnej Komunikácie Slovenskej Akadémie VIED	UVSK SAV	RPO	SK
8	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev	URAK	RPO	BG
9	Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información	GOBCAN	RFO	ES
10	Fundo Regional para a Ciencia e Tecnologia	FRCT	RFO	PT

1. What is ATHENA?

Project framework (I)

1. What is ATHENA?

Project framework (II)

1. What is ATHENA?

Project implementation

2. ATHENA context to pursue gender equality

Work Package 2 activities: Gender Equality Audit and assessment at organizational level

Database for Gender Equality Audit (D2.1)

Quantitative and qualitative Gender Equality indicators.

Dimensions:

1. Pool of graduate talents
2. Gender balance in research
3. Gender balanced career advancement
4. Gender balance in decision-making
5. Gender balanced working conditions
6. Gender balance in research outputs

2. ATHENA context to pursue gender equality

Work Package 2 activities: Gender Equality Audit and assessment at organizational level

Report on national status in gender equality in each partner country (D2.2)

Exhaustive assessment of the different international and national laws, policies and incentives in gender equality in research.

Content:

1. International and European Union commitments for gender equality in society and research and innovation.
2. Status of gender equality in the partners' countries.
3. Status of gender equality in research and higher education.
4. Conclusions and recommendations for each ATHENA country.

2. ATHENA context to pursue gender equality

Work Package 2 activities: Gender Equality Audit and assessment at organizational level

The diagram is a funnel-shaped process flow:

- Top: Assessment of existing national provisions and Qualitative and quantitative gender audits
- Middle: Identification of existing gender bias in RPOs and RFDs
- Bottom: Gender Equality reports

Conclusions for each ATHENA country	
Bulgaria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Officially supports the implementation of the Gender Equality Strategy adopted by the EC. • The country presents clear evidence of the encouraging behaviour of its institutions towards the goal of achieving gender equality.
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has a legal framework that incorporates the rights of equality between women and men. • Institutional mechanisms for gender equality and gender mainstreaming in Poland remain a key issue of relevance for policy and the role of the EU. • Different strategies, programs and action plans have been implemented by the State Research Agency, such as the creation of the Strategic Group of Gender Equality. • The gender pay gap between men and women in research is still present.
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accession to the EU has contributed to a general improvement of the legal framework for equality. • Institutional mechanisms for gender equality and gender mainstreaming in Poland remain a key issue of relevance for policy and the role of the EU. • One of the biggest challenges of gender (in)equality in science is the elimination of sexual harassment. • Both at the University and in other Research Organisations is a little awareness of gender equal opportunities in science.
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The European, national and regional legal-political framework promotes the promotion of gender equality at organisational level. • However, the mechanisms for technical support and control of the implementation of equality policies are still incipient.
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is a signatory state for all major European and international treaties in the field. • There is a lack of culture of evidence that makes difficult the design and implementation of national policies in any area. • At the moment, there is no integrative operational gender sensitive approach to educational policies at a whole.
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The primary legislation of gender equality is disclosed in the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act, which defines general and special measures for the creation of equal opportunities. • The relationship between gender equality and science/education is currently not balanced and different types of gender inequalities have been recognised. • Under the Ministry, there is a Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science, which is very active in the area.
Slovakia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The promotion of gender equality in most societal areas is backed by several national strategies and action equality plans. • Based on the gender equality indicators, the unequal and gender imbalanced situation has stalled and even worsened. • The overall commitment for gender equality in research, innovation and HEI is limited.

2. ATHENA context to pursue gender equality

Work Package 2 activities: Gender Equality Audit and assessment at organizational level

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

3. EU policies and initiatives for institutional change and GEPs

EU Framework & Policies: Timeline

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3. EU policies and initiatives for institutional change and GEPs

- The EU Council conclusions on 'Advancing gender equality in the European Research Area' called for cultural and institutional changes to address gender imbalances in research institutions and in decision-making bodies. Research performing (RPOs) and funding organisations (RFOs) were encouraged to implement institutional changes, in particular through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).
- The Commission, through Horizon 2020 programme, provided funds to research organizations aimed at implementing GEPs.

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3. EU policies and initiatives for institutional change and GEPs

Horizon Europe

Eligibility criterion

Participants (as beneficiaries and affiliated entities) that are public bodies, research organisations or higher education institutions established in a Member State or Associated Country must have a gender equality plan (GEP) in place, fulfilling mandatory process-related requirements.

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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

What is a GEP?

The EC considers a Gender Equality Plan as a set of actions aiming at:

1. Conducting **impact assessment / audits of procedures and practices** to identify gender bias;
2. Identifying and implementing **innovative strategies to correct any bias**;
3. **Setting targets and monitoring progress** via indicators.

Source: European Commission Communication on 'A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth' (COM(2012) 392 final)

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Phases

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

Getting started

- **Context matters!**
Identify the actions that would work best in your institution in accordance with its objectives and relevant national/regional contexts.
- **Involve the right people**
Involve gender experts, potential collaborators at different levels inside and outside the institution.

Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

Analysis

- **Analyse sex-disaggregated data**
Data broken by sex is needed to detect any gender differences and to identify the most pressing areas requiring intervention. Check which data are readily available and implement efforts to collect the data that do not exist yet in your institution.
- **Identify the existing measures that promote gender equality**
The results of the existing measures need to be assessed considering the potential measures to be involved. So, their effectiveness can be enhanced.

Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects

Planning (I)

- **Review measures implemented by other organisations**
Inspiration can be got by reviewing measures implemented by other organisations. Bear in mind that you should adapt these measures to your specific context.
Learn from ATHENA sister projects: <https://www.athenaequality.eu/about/>
- **Define SMART objectives and measures**
SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-related).
- **Define a realistic timeline for its implementation**
- **Promote the participation of actors at all levels**
By implementing a participatory approach, you may define meaning measures to the actors involved and will enhance their willingness to implement the measures in the GEP.

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Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects

Planning (II)

- **Set clear staff responsibilities for each measure.**
Clearly indicate who is responsible for what and when.
- **Build alliances**
Spend time to explain what a Gender Equality Plan implies for the targeted stakeholders. The measures of the GEP will not be achieved unless they are implemented by the stakeholders. These efforts should continue throughout the implementation phase of the GEP.
- **Consider sustainability**
To ensure sustainability, it is key to embed practices in the normal routines, policies and procedures of the institution.

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Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects

Implementation (I)

- **Try to embed and institutionalise as many actions/measures as possible**
This is important to ensure sustainability
- **Organise regular meetings**
It is important that the team responsible for the implementation of the GEP (the GEPI Committees) organize regular meetings to discuss progress, main achievements and aspects that can be improved. The regular meetings may also help identify any possible challenges or problems and act on them.
- **Plan meetings with high management and leadership, HR staff, researchers and professors, administrative staff and other co-workers you consider relevant**
This will help create ownership of the GEP and motivate the involved staff.

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Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects

Implementation (II)

- **Keep engaging stakeholders**
Engage stakeholders on an ongoing basis.
- **Communicate and give visibility to the Gender Equality Plan**
Utilize different channels to communicate the GEP, its main areas of intervention, timeframe and achievements.
- **Take in mind that the GEP may need adaptations**
A GEP is dynamic and may need modifications or amendments. Discuss with the GEPI Committee whether and how the GEP can be adapted.
- **Resistances and obstacles may exist**
Be prepared to face obstacles or resistances.

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Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

Monitoring (I)

- **Indicators should be implementation-oriented**
Indicators should be oriented to implementation and adapted to the purposes of the action.
- **Qualitative aspects should be also considered.**
- **Evaluate the results**
Evaluation is key to sustainability as it provides evidence of actual changes or lack of them and pave the way for future and more resolute actions, offering a valuable knowledge for their design.

Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

Monitoring (II)

- **Examples of quantitative indicators**
 - ✓ Number of female and male candidates for positions
 - ✓ Number of women and men in selection panels (for recruitment and promotion)
 - ✓ Horizontal sex segregation in respective categories of occupation
 - ✓ Number of male and female individuals targeted and reached by gender awareness-raising or planned training actions
 - ✓ Gender ratios in accessing research grants (and other resources, e.g. laboratory spaces or personnel)
 - ✓ Gender pay gap among different categories of staff , including researchers.

Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

Monitoring (III)

- **Examples of quantitative indicators**
 - ✓ The uptake of the gender equality objectives set by the Gender Equality Plan by different categories of stakeholders.
 - ✓ The actual transformation towards greater gender-sensitivity of both formal and informal practices as an effect of implemented actions.

Source: EIGE's Roadmap to Gender Equality Plans

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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Key aspects !

After the GEP

Despite the GEP will conclude at some point in time, this is not the end of promoting gender equality. A **new cycle should start and there might be actions that still require further action**, or new areas of attention may have been identified.

It should be decided how to continue the efforts undertaken so far and what a new GEP should address.

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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Main obstacles

- Resistance
- Lack of understanding of what gender equality and/or a GEP is
- Conviction that commitment to merit and/or excellence negates the need for gender equality work and/or GEPs
- Perception that gender equality work is not required
- Lack of autonomy of RPOs and RFOs
- Lack of sufficient, on-going resources: human and financial
- Lack of institutional or organisation authority
- Lack of relevant data and statistics
- Not engaging potential key allies and/or actors early
- Absence of a historical background in gender studies within the institution
- Ensuring the sustainability and resilience of gains related to gender equality
- Narrow understanding of research funding activities

Source: EIGE

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Horizon Europe

Eligibility criterion

Mandatory GEP process requirements

<p>Public document</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal document • Signed by top management • Published on the institution's website • Disseminated through institution 	<p>Dedicated resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding for gender equality positions or teams • Reserved time for others to work on gender equality 	<p>Data collection and monitoring</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on sex or gender of staff across roles and leadership • Annual reports and evaluation of progress and outcomes 	<p>Training and capacity building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whole organisation engagement • Tackle gender biases of people and decisions • Joint action on specific topics
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4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Recommended GEP content areas

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

ATHENA Wheel for GEPs

- GEP content areas
- GEP domain within the area
- GEP actions/measures

4. Gender Equality Plans in RPOs and RFOs

Definition of actions

Action No.	Content area	Issue to be addressed/evidence	Planned action	Start/end date	Person responsible	Success measures	Impact assessment	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Work-life balance and organisational culture								
2	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making								
3	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression								
4	Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content								
5	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment								

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Tailored worksheets

- Register to the ATHENA e-platform: www.gender-equality.eu
- Access this training 'Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe'.
- Access 'Lecture 2 - ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)'.
- At the **bottom of the page**, you will find the **additional material to be completed offline and that is adapted to each ATHENA target group**.
- Complete the worksheet PDF file and submit it by **uploading it to the e-platform**.

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Thank you for your attention!

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Worksheets

<p>SG5: Leadership.</p> <p>SG6: Sexual and sex-related harassment.</p> <p>SG7: Communication.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
<p>Task 4: ATHENA Wheel for Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Download the 'ATHENA Wheel for GEPs' you can find at the 'Lectures files' section, within the folder corresponding to your target group within ATHENA (high and middle management). 2. Referring to the ATHENA Wheel for GEPs, suggest two actions your unit/institution could take for the areas of 'Gender balance in leadership and decision-making', 'Work-life balance and organizational culture' and 'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment'. <p>To complete this task, you may consult the material used in the previous tasks 2 and 3.</p> <p>'Gender balance in leadership and decision-making' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>'Work-life balance and organizational culture' Action 1:</p> <p>Action2:</p> <p>'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
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Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Online course worksheet

- Lecture/Module 2: ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans
- ATHENA target group: [Researchers and professors](#)

Once attended the live session or watched the presentation of the module 2 'ATHENA approach for gender equality and Gender Equality Plans' of this online course, please utilize this worksheet to complete the online tasks.

You are encouraged to fully complete the tasks to benefit on building your knowledge and experience on institutional change management.

Once the worksheet is completed, please submit it by uploading to the ATHENA e-platform. You will find the 'Upload' button at the end of the site of the lecture.

Task 1: Video 'Gender Equality Action Plans. Equality and inclusion in Universities and Research Institutions'

Watch the video published by the ATHENA sister project 'Gearing Roles', in which change agents at various universities share their experiences in implementing their Gender Equality Action Plans.

Access the video [here](#).

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 2: Reading 'EIGE's examples of actions'

The EIGE's section on examples of actions provides successful measures towards gender equality. These actions are presented within 10 different gender equality areas:

1. Structures to support gender equality work.
2. Awareness-raising and competence development.
3. Engaging stakeholders.
4. Organisational culture and work-life balance.
5. Recruitment, selection and career progression support.
6. Leadership and decision-making.
7. Combatting sexual and gender-based harassment.
8. Integrating gender in research and education content.
9. Analytical measures, targets, indicators, monitoring and evaluation.
10. Incentive to promote gender equality.

Based on your competences and role within your institution, select one of the 10 areas presented and read each of its examples of actions.

Access the article [here](#).

Once you have read the examples of actions, please answer the following questions.

- a) Which area did you select?

- b) Which action caught your attention the most and why?

- c) In relation to the action that most caught your attention, please detail what are your initial thoughts.

Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.

Task 3: Have a look at the 'University of Deusto Equality Plan (2020-2022)'.

Have a look at the University of Deusto Equality Plan (2020-2022), developed and implemented under the framework of the 'Gearing roles' project. Read the plan paying particular attention to how the Plan is structured (the different sections that compose it). Specifically, read the measures and actions of the following Specific Goals (SG) within the section 7 on 'Measures and actions' (pages 18-24):

- SG3: Co-responsible conciliation.
- SG4: Teaching and research.
- SG6: Sexual and sex-related harassment.
- SG7: Communication.

Access the Plan [here](#).

Once you have taken a look at the Plan and have read the measures and actions of the specified SGs, please complete the following questions:

- a) Is there any measure(s) you would transfer and adapt to your institution? Specify the measures you would transfer for each specific goal (SG).

SG3: Co-responsible conciliation.

<p>SG4: Teaching and research.</p> <p>SG6: Sexual and sex-related harassment.</p> <p>SG7: Communication.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
<p>Task 4: ATHENA Wheel for Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Download the 'ATHENA Wheel for GEPs' you can find at the 'Lectures files' section, within the folder corresponding to your target group within ATHENA (researchers and professors).2. Referring to the ATHENA Wheel for GEPs, suggest two actions your unit/institution could take for the areas of 'Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content', 'Work-life balance and organizational culture' and 'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment'. <p>To complete this task, you may consult the material used in the previous tasks 2 and 3.</p> <p>'Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content' Action 1:</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Action 2:</p> <p>'Work-life balance and organizational culture' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
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<p>SG2: Wage gap – Combat the possible existence of a salary gap in equivalent positions.</p> <p>SG6: Sexual and sex-related harassment.</p> <p>SG7: Communication.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
<p>Task 4: ATHENA Wheel for Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Download the 'ATHENA Wheel for GEPs' you can find at the 'Lectures files' section, within the folder corresponding to your target group within ATHENA (HR professionals). 2. Referring to the ATHENA Wheel for GEPs, suggest two actions your unit/institution could take for the areas of 'Gender equality in recruitment and career progression', 'Work-life balance and organizational culture' and 'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment'. <p>To complete this task, you may consult the material used in the previous tasks 2 and 3.</p> <p>'Gender equality in recruitment and career progression' Action 1:</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Action 2:</p> <p>'Work-life balance and organizational culture' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
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<p>SG3: Co-responsible conciliation.</p> <p>SG6: Sexual and sex-related harassment.</p> <p>SG7: Communication.</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
<p>Task 4: ATHENA Wheel for Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Download the 'ATHENA Wheel for GEPs' you can find at the 'Lectures files' section, within the folder corresponding to your target group within ATHENA (Administrative staff). Referring to the ATHENA Wheel for GEPs, suggest three actions your unit/institution could take for the areas of 'Work-life balance and organizational culture' and 'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment'. <p>To complete this task, you may consult the material used in the previous tasks 2 and 3.</p> <p>'Work-life balance and organizational culture' Action 1:</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Action 2:</p> <p>Action 3:</p> <p>'Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment' Action 1:</p> <p>Action 2:</p> <p>Action 3:</p> <p>Tick the box on the right once this task is completed.</p>	
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ATHENA Wheel for Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

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Annex III – Evaluation form of the trainings 1 and 2 carried out via the ATHENA e-platform

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Training for ATHENA GEPI Committees: Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Evaluation form

1. As far as the lecture/module is concerned, how would you rate your online experience with module 1 from 1 to 5 being 1 Dissatisfied and 5 Very satisfied?

2. Compared to your expectations, how would you rate the activity?

4. To what extent do you consider the contents of the module meets its objectives from 1 to 5 being 1 The content of the module does not meet the objectives at all and 5 The content of the module fully meets the objectives?

5. Did you complete the additional offline activity tailored to each ATHENA target group?

7. Do you have any suggestions on how we could improve future ATHENA online events?

Send

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Annex IV – Templates for the specific tailored trainings

Annex IV.a – Training proposal template

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Capacity building for ATHENA GEPI Committees Training 3 – Tailored training to each ATHENA RPO/RFO

Training proposal template

[Insert here name of the ATHENA institution]

Training proposal outline
Training topic
Rationale for the training <i>[why there is a need for this training]</i>
Objectives of the training <i>[what is intended to achieve with the training]</i> Overall objective: Specific objectives:
Structure and proposed duration of the training Total duration: <i>[total number of hours]</i> Days on which it will take place: Day 1: <i>[DD/MM/YYYY]</i> Number of hours day 1: Day 2: <i>[DD/MM/YYYY]</i> Number of hours day 2: <i>Include more days if necessary</i>
Content <i>[Include the content to be covered]</i> Module 1: <i>[Name of module 1]</i> 1.) XXX 2.) XXX 3.) XXX Module 2: <i>[Name of module 2]</i> 1.) XXX 2.) XXX

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3.) XXX
Module X: XXX

Material [detail the material you will generate for the training (PPT presentation, infographics, etc.)]

Tools and techniques to be used

Agenda

[Include here the proposed agenda including timing for each day of training and for each module]

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Annex IV.b – Event report template

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Capacity building for ATHENA GEPI Committees

Event report and monitoring

[Insert here name of the ATHENA institution]

Venue	
Date	
Full name of the expert delivering the training	
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	
Total number of participants	
Number of high and middle managers participants	
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	
Duration of the training (hours)	
Format (classroom lesson, etc.)	

- Agenda of the event

[Please include here the agenda of the event]

- Pictures of the event

[Please include here a couple of nice pictures of the event]

- Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

- Methodology/Content/techniques

Please describe the methodology and content of the training:

Max. one page

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Please describe the tools and techniques used:

Max. half page

- Participants' feedback, main success and difficulties

Ask participants for feedback at the end of the training and please, report on:

- Viewpoints and suggestions on the aspects they liked most and they would improve.
- Specific relevant comments made by participants.

Max. half page

Please briefly describe main success and difficulties related to this specific training. Provide also improvement suggestions for the future trainings that will be carried out under T3.3.

Max. half page

Please include the links to the news on webpages and social media where the training has been disseminated.

www.athenaequality.eu

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